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ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF THE PEDAGOGICAL MASTERSHIP DEVELOPMENT OF THE MUSICAL ART TEACHER UNDER CONDITIONS OF POSTGRADUATE PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

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Стаття присвячена висвітленню актуальних проблем розвитку педагогічної майстерності вчителів музичного мистецтва в системі післядипломної педагогічної освіти. Розглянуто сучасний досвід з розвитку педагогічної майстерності вчителів музичного мистецтва в формальній освіті. Описано досвід виконання тематичних, авторських курсів, навчання педагогів на основі спецкурсів, майстер-класів, творчих майстерень, поглибленого тренінгового, тематичного навчання. Подано опис інноваційних форм навчання вчителів в курсовий період. Розглянуто досвід організації неформальної освіти з визначеної проблеми. Описано найбільш уживані форми підготовки педагогів в неформальній освіті як науково-педагогічні конференції, семінари-практикуми, тренінги, майстер-класи, круглі столи, проблемні теоретично-практичні семінари, методичні наради, школи педагогічної майстерності, участь педагогів в діяльності творчих груп, творчих об'єднань.

Описано досвід організації професійного саморозвитку вчителів музичного мистецтва в умовах інформальної освіти, що базується на основі сучасних мережових, електронних форм самонавчання педагогів. Визначено необхідність підготовки індивідуальних програм розвитку педагогічної майстерності для ефективного навчання педагогів. Описано результати досліджень в системі післядипломної педагогічної освіти, які демонструють виявлені пріоритети щодо видів і форм навчання серед вчителів музичного мистецтва. Визначено шляхи упровадження новітніх форм навчання з проблеми розвитку педагогічної майстерності вчителів музичного мистецтва в системі післядипломної педагогічної освіти. Серед перспектив розвитку педагогічної майстерності вчителів в післядипломній освіті визнано змістовне наповнення дистанційного, мережового, електронного навчання педагогів, добір ефективних технологій навчання, формування банку інноваційних форм і методів, підготовку науково-методичного супроводу процесу навчання вчителів музичного мистецтва в післядипломній педагогічній освіті

Ключові слова: педагогічна майстерність, вчителі музичного мистецтва, післядипломна педагогічна освіта, форми навчання

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1. Introduction

In the reforming period of the system of postgraduate pedagogical education the special attention of many researchers is fixed on problems of content and forms of teaching educators. An organic component of the native education is artistic education, which tasks are realized by teachers of musical art at general educational institutions. Fundamental training of teachers of musical art to the professional competence and pedagogical mastership development allows to raise the pedagogical labor quality and educational process efficiency of art school education. During decades the native experience of using active forms and methods of training musical art teachers in formal and non-formal education was created. Consideration of urgent problems of this topic allows to reveal a positive native experience as to the pedagogical mastership development of musical art teachers in different types of education and to point out ways and development prospects of pedagogical mastership within postgraduate pedagogical education.

2. Literature review

The review of the scientific-theoretical and methodical aspect of the pedagogical mastership development of teachers of the art branch in postgraduate pedagogical education allows to reveal conceptual positions

and methodological approaches that works of many scientists are devoted to [1, 2]. In scientific works teachers' pedagogical mastership is revealed as: the highest level of pedagogical activity; the complex of properties and qualities of a teacher's personality that provides the efficiency of his/her pedagogical activity on the reflexive base; the system of professional competences of a teacher; the pedagogical action technology [3, 4]. The consideration of possibilities of the system of postgraduate pedagogical education as to the improvement and development of teachers' pedagogical mastership that the works of many scientists are devoted to [5], allows to separate formal education as an effective type of education that influences the development of teacher's pedagogical mastership, including ones of art disciplines. Native scientists [6, 7] and teachers-practicians concentrate attention on the problem of forms and methods of non-formal education. And the question of informal education is considered in works [8] that demonstrate the most used technologies and forms for training teachers, modern development condition of non-formal education in Ukraine and foreign countries [8]. The problems of art knowledge development, professional development [9, 10] professional practice that influence teacher's mastership are considered in works of the native and foreign scientists [11, 12].

It is noted in the scientists' studies, that teachers' pedagogical mastership must be considered as a condition of the professional development of specialists that forms their professional competence and determine priority directions of the qualification improvement. Self-education of teachers and their involvement in scientific-pedagogical training forms in informal education must be considered as a necessary component of the system of postgraduate pedagogical education that attention of scientists-researchers is concentrated on [13].

So, the analysis of literary sources allowed to reveal that the question of the pedagogical mastership development in the art branch in postgraduate pedagogical education is urgent, the review of problems of the pedagogical mastership development of musical art teachers in different types of postgraduate education allows to reveal the positive native experience and to form ways of the further improvement of this problem.

3. Research aims and tasks

The aim of the study is to substantiate urgent problems of teachers' training for the pedagogical mastership development in different types of pedagogical education.

The following tasks were set for attaining this aim.

1. To consider the modern experience and to reveal innovative training forms for the pedagogical mastership development of musical art teachers in formal education;

2. To determine the most used training forms for the pedagogical mastership development of musical art teachers in non-formal education;

3. To describe the experience of organizing professional self-development of musical art teachers as a component of their pedagogical mastership under conditions of informal education;

4. To determine ways and prospects of introducing new training forms for the problem of pedagogical mastership development of musical art teachers in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education.

4. Urgent problems of training teachers for the pedagogical mastership development in different types of postgraduate pedagogical education

In the period of educational reforms attention of scientists, practitioners, specialists of the educational art branch is fixed on problems of art education content renovation, introduction of innovative training technologies, search for new forms of teaching integrated disciplines. Teachers' training for realizing innovations in the art educational branch will be organized more effectively, if integrity and succession of teachers' training is provided in all types of postgraduate pedagogical education. The analysis of literary-scientific sources, normative-legal documents testify to the necessity of improving formal, non-formal and informal types of education of teachers in the art branch.

The review of the practical experience of training teachers of art disciplines in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education allows to reveal most essential urgent problems of the pedagogical mastership development of musical art teachers.

The essential experience of improving qualification in formal education is accumulated in the system of modern postgraduate pedagogical education of musical art teachers. Development prospects of native postgraduate pedagogical education determine a necessity of providing the new quality of pedagogical and managerial education staff, able to realize the professional activity effectively under conditions of instability, uncertainty and permanent changes [14]. The system of postgraduate pedagogical education, as a fully organized, multifunctional, open, relatively independent educational one is directed on the progressive development and satisfaction of teachers' educational needs [15]. Postgraduate education determines the qualification improvement by enriching earlier acquired competences, gaining new and improving earlier acquired ones with the professional activity by a person [16].

Formal education is realized at educational institutions by curriculums and programs that correspond to educational training programs and requirements of the educational-qualification characteristic of specialists. The experience of using training technologies, forms and methods, directed on the teachers' pedagogical mastership development is accumulated in the course period within formal education of art musical teachers. Among most useful teachers' training forms there must be noted day, stationary and stationary-correspondence, distant training forms. Thus, different training forms at postgraduate pedagogical education institutions provide thematic author courses for developing pedagogical mastership of musical art teachers. In the structure of such courses the most effective training method for students is special courses, master-classes, creative workshops. Deepened training, thematic education with active forms and training methods has a theoretical-methodical, didactic, practical direction. During such training all components of teacher's pedagogical mastership develop actively. Lectures that form a base of scientific knowledge; practical, seminar activities that widen teachers' professional skills, and also thematic discussions, trainings, webinars that favor the pedagogical mastership development are necessary for training musical art teachers.

Innovative forms of training teachers include pedagogical coaching that provides the system character, vertical and horizontal integrity of the continuous educational postgraduate process. Integration of training, practical and self-educational teachers' activity is provided in the process of using pedagogical coaching [17].

The experience of training forms, directed on the pedagogical mastership development is accumulated within non-formal postgraduate education of musical art teachers. Scientific-pedagogical conferences, seminars (including online and offline Internet-conferences, seminars-practical works, trainings, master-classes, schools of pedagogical mastership must be related to widespread training forms in non-formal education. For reaching the most efficiency, training of musical art teachers is organized in temporal creative collectives, such as creative groups and associations. Thematic round tables, problem theoretical-practical seminars, psychological-pedagogical consili-

ums, methodic debates, series of master-classes, organized within the activity of teachers' methodical associations at the level of school, district or region, become effective training forms. Widespread training forms in non-formal education also include webinars, pedagogical marathons, creative workshops, organized using instruments of YouTube direct connection, and also training teachers at distant platforms. The development of distant education resulted in spreading thematic training for teachers, organized by means of digital technologies. Distant training as an effective form of non-formal education has a lot of possibilities for the pedagogical mastership development of teachers. Such training provides experience exchange, spread of technologies of the teachers' pedagogical mastership development, practical probation of innovative forms and methods of the teachers' pedagogical mastership improvement and so on. The native experience proves the effectiveness of the teachers' special mastership improvement in centers of pedagogical mastership that function at experimental educational institutions. The activity of such centers provides spreading best pedagogical ideas and forms of professional self-development at conducting scientific-pedagogical, methodical arrangements, pedagogical competitions, festivals of pedagogical ideas and so on.

Informal education, as one of links of postgraduate pedagogical education, realizes the problem of musical art teachers' pedagogical mastership development, based on network, electronic forms of teachers' self-education with a personal program, based on individual professional requirements, needs of teachers. The active development of electronic self-training at distant platforms, conditions for effective informal education of teachers are created in network pedagogical communities. Teachers' self-training for the pedagogical mastership development is conducted, based on individual programs of the pedagogical mastership development, programs of personal efficiency, acmeograms and so on [18]. Self-education of a teacher as a leading form of the professional competence improvement, gives a teacher a possibility to master, to widen and to deepen knowledge, to generalize the experience of pedagogical mastership by the purposeful, system, self-educational work, directed on self-development and self-improvement of a person, oriented on satisfying own interests and objective needs of an educational institution [19]. Taking into account the professional pedagogical experience, pedagogical qualification category of teachers, based on an individual educational trajectory, teachers determine forms and methods for improving the pedagogical mastership level, choose a self-training subject, plan the participation in e-courses, seminars, master-classes.

Based on the results of the research, conducted among teachers, who were an audience of qualification improvement courses and participants of scientific-pedagogical arrangement, it has been revealed, that musical art teachers in the first turn note possibilities of thematic and author courses within formal education as most effective training forms, directed on the teachers' pedagogical mastership development, and also prefer innovative forms of practice-oriented and training-oriented learning within non-formal education. Teach-

ers acknowledged the effectiveness of innovative self-training forms for the teachers' pedagogical mastership development, but determine a need for preparing teachers for organizing electronic and network self-training [20–22].

So, considering urgent problems of the musical art teachers' pedagogical mastership development in different forms of postgraduate pedagogical education, there must be noted a need in promising forms of teachers' training. Among prospects of the musical art teachers' pedagogical mastership development there must be noted the effectiveness of innovative forms of distant, network and electronic training of teachers [23, 24]. Additional efforts are needed for determining a content filling of training with using technologies of mixed and distant training, selection of urgent topics of teachers' education within pedagogical mastership, and also separation of effective training technologies and formation of a bank of innovative forms and methods at the teachers' pedagogical mastership development, based on digital technologies in formal, non-formal and informal education. Realization of the outlined ways of improving the problem becomes possible at the fundamental scientific-methodical support of the training process for musical art teachers.

5. Research results

In the process of analyzing sources it was revealed, that teachers' pedagogical mastership is considered as: the highest level of pedagogical activity; the complex of properties and qualities of a teacher's personality that provides the efficiency of his/her pedagogical activity on the reflexive base; the system of professional competences of a teacher; the pedagogical action technology. The study of urgent problems of musical art teachers' pedagogical mastership development under conditions of postgraduate pedagogical education allowed to reveal the most effective forms of training teachers within formal, non-formal and informal education, to find innovative tendencies in training and to outline ways and prospects of the chosen problem. The conclusions, obtained as a result of the work, don't pretend for an exhaustive solution of the problem of musical art teachers' pedagogical mastership development in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education. The work on this problem may be continued in the direction of studying questions of pedagogical conditions of musical art teachers' mastership in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education.

6. Conclusions

So, the problem of musical art teachers' pedagogical mastership development in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education is rather urgent. The study of urgent problems of musical art teachers' pedagogical mastership development in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education allowed to make the following conclusions:

1) The review of the modern experience of musical art teachers' pedagogical mastership development in formal education allowed to reveal the effective forms of training teachers that include thematic author courses. The innovative training forms of the musical art teach-

ers' pedagogical mastership development in formal education include master-classes, creative workshops and deepened training, thematic learning of theoretical-methodical, didactic, practical directionality and pedagogical coaching;

2) the most used effective forms of training teachers for the musical art teachers' pedagogical mastership development in non-formal education include: scientific-pedagogical conferences, seminars-practical works, trainings, master-classes, round tables, problem theoretical-practical seminars, methodical debates, series of master-classes, schools of pedagogical mastership, teachers' participation in the activity of creative groups and associations and also Internet-arrangements (webinars, pedagogical marathons, creative workshops);

3) the experience of organizing art musical teachers' professional self-development under condi-

tions of informal education is based on modern network, electronic forms of teachers' self-training. The necessity of effective training motivates the need for preparing teachers to creating individual development programs of pedagogical mastership, taking into account an experience and qualification category of teachers;

4) There were determined the ways of introducing new training forms for the problem of musical art teachers' pedagogical mastership development in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education. Development prospects of this problem were considered as a content filling of distant, network, e-learning of teachers, selection of effective learning technologies, formation of a bank of innovative forms and methods, the need to prepare fundamental scientific and methodological support for training musical art teachers in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education.

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